

A Neuroanatomical Review of Descending Motor Tracts in Animals: Implications for Translation in Regenerative Spinal Cord Injury Research

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ABSTRACT

Traumatic spinal cord injury (SCI) affects thousands of individuals every year globally with a higher incidence in the United States. Although it remains the subject of active research there are currently no FDA approved therapies or treatments for regeneration of the spinal motor tracts necessary for locomotion. Furthermore, there is no single source for neuroanatomical comparison of these spinal motor tracks across pre-clinical models of SCI. In this review we briefly describe the function of the corticospinal, rubrospinal, and vestibulospinal tracts across animal species used for SCI research before detailing the anatomy of each tract. We then compare neuroanatomical features of these tracks to human spinal cord. To conduct this review we consulted, PUBMED, Academic Search Ultimate, EBSCO Host, EBSCO eBooks, Google Scholar, and clinical textbooks. We determined that there are important differences between the origin, propagation, and termination of the locomotor tracts across different preclinical models. We identified a large gap in knowledge for the anatomy of swine motor tracts. Neuroanatomical differences are among reasons commonly cited for the lack effective translation of treatments from animal models to humans. Thus, understanding these differences is crucial for translation of therapies from preclinical models to human SCI. Given that large animals serve as an important intermediate for translation between rodent and human SCI this review provides a framework to understand these differences and comparison to human spinal tracks with the goal to contribute to the translational success of future therapies for SCI.

Keywords: Spinal cord injury, animal models, motor tract, corticospinal, rubrospinal, vestibulospinal

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1. INTRODUCTION

Traumatic spinal cord injury (SCI) is estimated to affect 13 people out of 100,000 per year. In North America, this figure doubles to 26/100,000 individuals, also leading to a high financial impact on patients.¹⁻³ While large animals such as cats have been used for SCI research in the past, rodents are the current standard due to availability of equipment and techniques, as well as cost⁴. However, the fundamental neuroanatomical and physiological differences between humans and preclinical models of SCI contributes to the challenge of translating experimental treatments from the laboratory into a clinical setting.⁴⁻⁸ This review focuses on the anatomical significance, and clinical relevance of three descending motor pathways: the corticospinal (CST), rubrospinal (RST) and vestibulospinal (VST) tracts. We compare the anatomy of each descending tract, including origin, propagation, decussation, and termination of these tracts between pre-clinical SCI models. A special emphasis is placed on the juxtaposition between published journal and medical literature as it pertains to the human tracts. Furthermore, the translation and efficacy of swine, cat, and rodents as models for human traumatic spinal cord injury treatments are evaluated. Lastly, the current clinical status of regenerative spinal cord therapies is described.

2. PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF SCI & NEED FOR TRANSLATION

The current model of spinal cord injury characterizes two phases: primary injury and secondary injury.⁹⁻¹¹ In the primary phase, the spinal cords vertebrae are physically traumatized: ligaments are torn, and the glial membrane is destroyed.⁹⁻¹¹ Current research also suggests that the SCI effects are the intensity of the vertebrae damage and the amount of time that the spinal cord spends compressed.⁹⁻¹¹

The secondary injury phase of the spinal cord is best described through the changes in pathophysiology and biochemistry due to the primary injury.^{11,12} Secondary injury can be further categorized into three phases: the acute, the sub-acute phase (which only presents should the acute phase remain for an extend period), and the chronic phase.^{11,13,14} The acute phase presents a robust inflammatory response with features such as the increased presence of free radicals, damage to spinal cord-associated vessels, and tissue death.^{11,13,14} Should the acute injury phase effect itself for an extended period of time, the following aspects of the sub-acute phase are observed (the following is a non-exhaustive list): neuron death, scars of glial cells, along with changes of axon structure.^{11,13} Lastly, the chronic phase of SCI is defined by the presence of a cystic cavity, axonal dieback, and the progression of glial scar formation.^{11,13,14}

After a traumatic SCI, there is evidence that the affected area undergoes cortico-remapping. Originally described as a characteristic of the sensory nervous system, cortico-remapping involves changing the location of cortex-functions to another area of the brain.¹⁵ Evidence for the presence of this phenomenon does exist for the CST, but its general complexities and unique cellular properties (biochemical changes in receptor-ligand activity as well as elongated neural structure) which proves challenging for the artificial rearrangement of pathways.¹⁶⁻¹⁸

The clinical progress of spinal cord regeneration and repair is aimed primarily towards axon regeneration, although other goals certainly exist.¹⁹ Although inconsistently used, axon regeneration is best described by²⁰ as: (after incomplete or complete damage) the growth from the origin of the damage (cut) to the proper axon termination point observed in an undamaged axon. A scientific consensus of regeneration and other terms pertaining to axon behavior after injury (either naturally observed or artificially induced) has not yet been reached, which contributes to confusion regarding the conclusion of contemporary research.²⁰ The complexity of the corticospinal tract (critically important and used extensively in for humans for motor control), proves research regarding regenerative properties significantly challenging.²⁰

3. SPECIES-SPECIFIC TRACT ANATOMY

3.1 CORTICOSPINAL TRACT

The corticospinal tract (CST) is primarily involved in the control and coordination of motor inputs.²¹ In coordination with the primary motor cortex and other descending motor tracts, the CST is responsible for, relaying and effecting vertebrate limb motor function²². Humans have an extensive cortical system, containing up to two times as many neurons in a single pyramidal fiber than other species.²³ The human CST has two descending pathways to control movement of muscles in the limbs, as well as movement of the muscles in the trunk, neck and shoulders.²² Research has suggested that the pig CST closely resembles that of humans, with similar parallel descending pathways, but with fewer projections.²⁴ Conversely, studies in rodents and cats suggest the CST does not play as significant of a role in locomotion as the rubrospinal tract.^{8,25-29} Understanding the differences and similarities of this tract between pre-clinical models of SCI and with human SCI is of particular significance due to its involvement in motor recovery following damage to the spinal cord.²¹

3.1.1 SWINE

There is currently limited knowledge regarding the CST of pigs. Early research focused around establishing the existence of the CST in pigs using cortical electrode mapping and lesion studies suggested that the corticospinal tract did not exist in swine.³⁰ However, more recent work by our group and others have used anterograde tracers to demonstrate that the CST is indeed present in the porcine spinal cord as a means of controlling motor behavior.^{24,30,31} In fact, these data show that the porcine CST is more homologous to that of humans compared to rodents, which suggests pig models of SCI have high translational fidelity for assessing motor recovery.

Origin

Contemporary work identifies two major contributors of corticospinal fibers: the primary motor cortex and the premotor cortex.²⁴ Neurons from the motor cortex descend ipsilaterally through the midbrain and medulla oblonga. Other key traits of the primary motor cortex include a low density of neurons in cell layer III, a high density of nerve cells distributed widely across layer V in addition to oblong cells in layer VI and giant Betz cells.^{32,33} Lower amounts of fibers descend through the dorsomedial and ventromedial funiculi.²⁴

Decussation

84.9% of fibers decussate at the pyramids and progress through the spinal cord primarily via the contralateral dorsolateral funiculus to the sixth thoracic vertebrae (T6).^{24,34} Fibers decussating with respect to the midline have been described as well, specifically pertaining to the spinal cord itself.²⁴ Further, small proportions of the fibers have been observed in the dorsolateral and ventromedial funiculi.³⁴ Findings also report that 84.9% of the fibers cross over rostrally with respect to the second cervical vertebrae (C2), and that the tract runs primarily through the dorsolateral funiculus.²⁴

Termination

Regardless of origin, fibers were found descending past C2 to T6, although the presence of CST axons in lower levels (T7 and on), has been described as a possibility.²⁴ While both tracts originate in the motor cortex and descend in a similar manner, the fibers originating from the primary cortex are responsible for the corticorubral connections.²⁴ The presence of nerve cells at C2, which travelled down to the T6 of the spinal cord, has also been observed, and occurs independent of their origin.²⁴

3.1.2 RAT

Early investigation of the rat CST was largely performed using electrophysiology combined with the classical tractography techniques, such as lesion analysis and wheat germ agglutinin-horseradish peroxidase (WGA-HRP) tracing, among others.³⁵⁻³⁸ Variation in the time of analysis (developmental vs. adult), investigative methods (tracing vs. lesions/electrophysiology), and imaging technology of the time limited early characterization and specificity of the rat CST.³⁵⁻³⁸ Despite these limitations, the earliest tractography experiments were still able to elucidate fundamental information on both form and function of the CST, as well as its response to lesion.^{35,37,38} Current research involves validation and expansion of previous work, aided by advancements in the fields of tractography and the use of sophisticated vector-mediated fluorescent tracking, to increase specificity and resolution of the tract anatomy.^{39,40}

Origin

The rodent corticospinal tract begins in the motor cortex before descending in the corpus callosum.⁴¹

Decussation

After the corpus callosum fibers descend through the internal capsule, they decussate at the pyramids and propagate caudally through the spinal cord.⁴¹ A high proportion of fibers are assumed to decussate and continue contralaterally through the spinal cord (over 90%) relative to the ipsilateral fibers (10%).⁴¹ Decussation is responsible for the two major corticospinal tracts: the dorsal and ventral tracts.

The dorsal CST is considered the major tract where the majority of projections cross, which contrasts to the ventral CST, which is considered the minor tract, with fewer projections remain uncrossed.^{36,41-43} In the dorsal corticospinal tract, most (95%) of the neurons are present in the ventral aspect, with the remaining neurons residing in the ventral columns (present in the medial aspect, 3-5%).^{38,41,44} Histological assessment has been used to establish the anatomy of the corticospinal tract. Specifically, in rats, the CST descends caudally through the internal capsule, cerebral peduncle, longitudinal pontine fasciculus, pyramid and the pyramidal decussation, in addition to the dorsal fasciculus.⁴⁵⁻⁴⁷ To that extent, both the anatomy and the structure of the corticospinal tract have been verified by the use of manganese-enhanced magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) in rat specimens.²¹ This same procedure also verified that the corticospinal tract crosses at the pyramidal decussation.²¹

Termination – Ventral CST

Anterograde tracing using biotin dextran-amine (BDA) localized termination of the ventral CST to Rexed's laminae III and IV.⁴⁴ Termination has been observed in all vertebrae, when collaterals branch into grey matter and primarily Rexed's laminae III and IV.⁴⁴

Termination – Lateral CST

Similarly, an anterograde HRP experiment has established the termination of the lateral CST in the lateral white columns in the lumbar enlargement.⁴⁸

3.1.3 MOUSE

In mice, most of the information known about the CST arises from a few dedicated tractography studies. This work was completed relatively recently and uses a variety of methods, ranging from experimental genetics to more typical HRP, FluoroGold (FG), and 1,1'-dioctadecyl-3,3,3',3'-tetramethylindocarbocyanine (DiI) injections.⁴⁹⁻⁵¹ One application of special interest to tract tracing is light-sheet fluorescence microscopy (LFSM) which, while still in its infancy, is already providing new insights in defining specific connectivity of CST fibers between the brain and spinal cord.⁵² Although these details expand beyond the scope of this review, these new technologies will lead to an understanding of CST connections at the neuronal level.

Origin

A literature search has not commented on the existence of a separate dorsal and ventral CST. To the extent known, the origin of the CST in mice is believed to be the motor cortex, localized to the primary/secondary motor, and somatosensory cortices.⁴⁹ The low relative volume of cells when compared to other tracts (and predominant dorsal horn termination) has led some to believe that the CST has a larger role altering sensation in the spinal cord than it does motor function.⁵⁰ Retrograde labeling has further localized the origin to the forelimb and hindlimb areas of the motor cortex.⁵¹

The development of anterograde tracing methods has allowed for a more detailed characterization of mouse motor tracts. Particularly, the use of DiI injection into the motor cortex saw neurons exit the motor cortex, descend through the internal capsule, pyramidal peduncle, and basal pontine gray where collaterals could be observed.⁵¹

Decussation

Neurons are observed entering the pyramid, crossing the midline at the pyramids, and moving contralaterally beyond the dorsal funiculus.⁵¹ Terminal branches were observed in the ventral horn after the dorsal funiculus was passed.⁵¹

Termination

The fibers of the mouse CST have been evaluated many times using different techniques. Liang et al. have used retrograde tracing to localize termination to the dorsal horn of the cervical spine, specifically laminae C3-5.⁵⁰

3.1.4 CAT

Cat corticospinal axons have been shown to occupy a large volume of the spinal cord, and as a result are believed to influence many motoneurons. There is also currently evidence to suggest that in cats, the CST functions in conjunction with the rubrospinal tract to control the previously discussed movements.²⁷⁻²⁹

Investigation of the feline CST began early in the 1940's, with histological staining and electrophysiology as the main tools for analysis.⁵³⁻⁵⁵ The capability of early investigative techniques, such as the use of silver staining, limited the fidelity of research during this time.⁵³ Tractography was then revisited with the advent of new tracing methods (HRP, Golgi Methods) and advancements in electrophysiology that enabled new techniques to yield higher-fidelity results.⁵⁶⁻⁵⁹ More recent cat CST research largely surrounds locomotion and its pathologies.⁶⁰⁻⁶² Below, we use a combination of literature to describe the cat CST.

Origin

Similar to primates and humans, the corticospinal tract in cats begins with neurons in the motor cortex, progress through the corpus callosum and the internal capsule.⁴¹ In cats, this is further localized to the primary motor cortex, which gave rise to dorsal and ventral CST fibers.⁵⁹ Of further importance, Armand and Kuypers also found the somatosensory cortices (primary and secondary) contribute to both the dorsal and ventral CSTs, but significantly more so to the dorsal tract.⁵⁹

Decussation

The cat CST crosses the midline in the pyramidal decussation before travelling down through the spinal cord.⁴¹ An estimated 75-95% of CST neurons cross the midline, with the remaining 25-5% of neurons progressing through the tract uncrossed. Armand and Kuypers corroborate this result, and report a 10:1 ratio of crossed to uncrossed fibers at levels C5-7 in the dorsolateral CST.⁵⁹ The same researchers found that the ventral CST demonstrated a much lower decussation ratio of 1:1.⁵⁹

Termination

Only termination of the lateral corticospinal tract is described in detail, as most experiments characterizing the cat CST use retrograde tracing methods to emphasize its cortical origins.^{57,58} Under that consideration, the majority of lateral CST fibers appear to terminate in Rexed's laminae IV, V, VI, and VII, with smaller contributions in laminae VIII and IX.⁵⁸ These results were consistent with similar work, as well.⁵⁶ Termination is known to take place at least down to the upper lumbar vertebrate.^{56,58}

3.1.5 HUMAN

Obvious ethical complications limit the direct investigation into human motor tracts to the extent that have been investigated in animals. Consequently, there is an extremely limited volume of investigations focused on the CST in human subjects, and work is largely limited to the use of diffusion weighted/tensor imaging (DWI/DTI) superior to the brainstem.⁶³⁻⁶⁵

Below, we describe the CST with respect to both published research from human data and from accepted medical textbooks. We provide additional information regarding the efficacy of each proposed animal model in the section titled "Comparison of models relevant to SCI research."

Origin

Anatomical textbooks extrapolate data from large animals (specifically primates) to infer information about the human CST.⁶⁶ Although the CST is believed to originate from many different regions of the cortex, the primary contributors (Betz cells) originate in the prefrontal cortex.⁶⁶ The tract then descends via subcortical white matter to the posterior limb of the anterior capsule. After which, the corticospinal neurons descend through the ventral midbrain, located in the cerebral peduncle (crus cerebri), moving through the caudal side of the pons before pontocerebellar fibers

distinguish the CST from the medulla's ventral surface.⁶⁶ Often the CST is referenced as a *pyramidal tract*, owing to its formation of a bundle in the medulla oblongata which is described as a pyramid. The neurons coalesce into the pyramid after passing through the medulla oblongata, creating a characteristic grouping of cells found on the medulla's ventral surface.⁶⁶

Decussation

After the pyramid, the CST descends further to the pyramidal decussation, where 75-90% of the neurons cross.⁶⁶ Neurons that have decussated are now defined as the lateral corticospinal tract. While the majority of CST cells decussate to the lateral CST, a low number of fibers remain ipsilateral and are known as the anterior (or ventral) CST.⁶⁶ The anterior CST decussates in the spinal cord immediately prior to termination on a lower motor neuron.

Termination

The lateral CST then descends, and decreases in size as it does so, through the lateral funiculus in an oblong manner before terminating in the ventral horn of the spinal cord at the fourth sacral vertebrae (S4) on ipsilateral nerve cells.⁶⁶

The anterior corticospinal tract is comprised of the remaining 10-25% uncrossed fibers, and continues through the ventral funiculus, decreasing in size as it progresses through the spinal cord until it is no longer detectible in the midthoracic vertebrae.⁶⁶ The cells of this tract span the midline at the ventral white commissure, allowing for communication with contralateral nerve cells.⁶⁶

Animal and limited human spinal cord analyses propose that the human CST terminates in the lateral aspects of laminae IV, V, and VI as well as both laterally and medially in laminae VII.⁶⁶ In laminae IV-VI, termination is contralateral. Bilateral termination in lamina VIII has also been observed, supplementary to contralateral motoneuron lamina IX (dorsolateral component) and laterally in central and ventrolateral types.⁶⁶ Cells associated with the frontal cortex conclude primarily on lamina V, VI, VII, VIII interneurons, although the majority are associated with the VI's laminae.⁶⁶ With respect to parietal CST origins, termination largely occurs in the contralateral dorsal horn in addition to laminae IV, V, and VI (laterally) and lamina VII (also laterally).⁶⁶ Lastly, those with origins in the sensory cortex terminate in laminae IV and V.⁶⁶

3.2 RUBROSPINAL TRACT

The rubrospinal tract (RST) is another important descending motor pathway that controls limb movement, particularly related to flexion and extension. Diffusion tensor imaging studies have struggled to ascertain useful information about the innervation and function of the human RST; discoveries of RST function have primarily been founded by research in primates.⁶⁶⁻⁶⁹ The interaction of the RST with other sensory and motor tracts and low volume in humans complicates identifying its function, which pales in comparison to what is known of the CST.^{8,23,70,71} The RST has yet to be defined in pigs, although both rodent and cat studies have identified the RST as a primary motor pathway. Tract tracing in cats has shown the RST controls muscles in the distal forelimb.⁷² Rodents primarily use the rubrospinal tract for motion, compared to the human use of the corticospinal tract.⁸ To that effect, rodents rely on the CST for specific motor control of forelimbs.^{7,22,73} Further tract tracing work implicates the neurons of the supplementary motor area with head and neck movements and interactions with the RST in rat.⁷⁴ This idea is similar in mice, where the RST is believed to be significantly important in locomotion, illustrated by the large volume of neurons populating this tract relative to the small size of the mouse.⁷⁵

Across all species, the rubrospinal tract is believed to originate in the caudal area of the red nuclei, referred to as magnocellular).^{76,77} The tract then descends through the spinal cord in the dorsolateral funiculus after crossing over itself at the tegmental decussation^{76,78}

3.2.1 SWINE

Despite an intensive search across PubMed, Google Scholar, Access Medicine, no articles describing the rubrospinal tract of swine were found. Key terms include "swine rubrospinal tract", "rubrospinal tract of swine", "porcine rubrospinal tract", and "pig rubrospinal tract". Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that there is limited, if any, knowledge pertaining to the form or function of the swine RST. Interestingly, early work in pigs defined the morphology and cytoarchitecture of the red nucleus, which is known as the site of origin of the RST.⁷⁹ Using histological assessment, Otabe and Horowitz found that the ventral tegmental decussation was well developed in pigs, which suggests pigs have a rubrospinal tract homologous to other mammals although this has yet to be defined.⁷⁹

3.2.2 RAT

Despite the rubrospinal tract being widely researched and characterized in other animals, a detailed understanding of the RST has not been investigated to the same degree that the CST has in rodents.⁷⁶ Scientific interest in the RST began much later than other tracts, around the 1970's. Explicit tractography experiments around the conception of the RST are rare, as most of this work was performed through lesion analysis and experimental treatments.⁸⁰⁻⁸³ However, the rat RST has been evaluated to some extent using injection of dyes paired with histological reconstruction, spanning a developmental range of neonate to adult.^{76,78,80,81}

Origin

Red nuclei (stated above), before largely concentrating in the contralateral dorsolateral fundus and contacting all vertebra of the spinal cord^{76,77,84}.

Decussation

As stated above, the rat RST is believed to decussate at the tegmental decussation.⁷⁶

Termination

The crossed fibers have been shown to terminate mainly throughout Rexed's laminae (IV, V, and VI), as well as occasionally to the dorsal component of lamina III and the ventral component of lamina VII.⁷⁶ The presence of rubrospinal cells is rarely observed in the ventral part of the spinal cords gray matter (laminae IV).⁷⁶ The rat rubrospinal tract has recently been found to be present in the cervical vertebrae, specifically Rexed's IX lamina.⁷⁶

3.2.3 MOUSE

Experiments solely dedicated to the mouse RST are sparse. Liang et al. performed a dedicated investigation of the rubrospinal tract using Fluorogold and biotinylated dextran amine (BDA) paired with immunohistochemistry.⁷⁵ Current research into rubrospinal circuitry is largely genetic in nature and leverages genetic knock out methods and optogenetics to evaluate tract changes.⁸⁵⁻⁸⁷

Origin

The mouse RST is believed to originate in the red nucleus, with contributions from the rostral and caudal aspects⁷⁵. When injected rostrally, tracers descended medially to both the intermediate nucleus of the lateral lemniscus and the trigeminal nerve.⁷⁵ The RST fibers were shown to run between the motor trigeminal nucleus and the principal sensory trigeminal nucleus, before associating with the ventrolateral surface of the hindbrain.⁷⁵ The fibers would descend medially to the spinal trigeminal nerve and ventrolateral to the facial nucleus and maintained this position throughout the hindbrain.⁷⁵ Current analysis establishes a high degree of ambiguity between the rostral and caudal red nucleus in the mouse, as labeled neurons have been detected in both parts of the red nucleus.⁷⁵ Of note, neurons projecting to the lumbar spinal cord were located more ventrolaterally in the rostral red nucleus compared to projections to the cervical spinal cord that were located more medially.⁷⁵

Decussation

Anterograde BDA injections have shown decussation of the mouse RST to take place at the ventral tegmental decussation before travelling caudally.⁷⁵ When travelling through the spinal cord, the RST has been observed in the dorsolateral aspect of the lateral funiculus, ventral to the lateral spinal nucleus, contralateral to its origin.⁷⁵

Termination

Mouse RST terminates primarily in laminae V, VI, and VII (dorsal part only), with some fibers terminating in laminae VIII and X.⁷⁵ Fibers ipsilateral to the origin were also detected in these laminae, but with fewer fibers and projections compared to the contralateral side.⁷⁵ Termination is observed from levels C8-T1 in both ipsilateral and contralateral tracts, but only the contralateral RST terminates in the lower lumbar regions (L5-6) of the spinal cord.⁷⁵

3.2.4 CAT

The feline RST is relatively more well defined compared to that of the rodent. Early tracing projects primarily made use of tissue staining and electrophysiology to understand the RST's form and function.⁸⁸⁻⁹⁰ Some early conclusions reached through this work was that the RST is largely conserved amongst vertebrates, which has obvious implications where SCI modeling is concerned.⁹⁰ Early radioactive amino acid analysis has pointed to the presence of an ipsilateral rubrospinal component in addition to the already established contralateral projections.⁹⁰⁻⁹² Research activity regarding

feline neuroanatomy has been in decline since the 2000's, and current areas of interest include electrophysiology and experimental SCI treatment.^{62,93,94}

Origin

The cat rubrospinal tract begins in the red nucleus (in small medium and large cells).^{90,91}

Decussation

The majority of feline RST fibers cross at the tegmental RST decussation within the brain.^{76,78} Contralateral fibers descending through the sacral vertebrae has been observed.^{90,91} Additional research has described a crossover between the corticospinal and rubrospinal tracts.⁹⁵ This is primarily observed in the cervical region of spinal cord, but it should be noted that this phenomenon is observed in the lumbar region as well, although to a far lesser extent.⁹⁵ In the cervical vertebrae, neurons are found to be connected to both the rubrospinal and corticospinal tracts, as well as each track independently.⁹⁵ However, the coalescence between the two tracts does not indicate that a collaboration of the two descending tracts is necessary, but is likely an important redundancy when thinking about recovery of sensorimotor function following spinal cord injury.⁹⁵ This is evident by the existence of neurons associated with only one tract, further suggesting variability across the diameter of RST fibers.⁹⁵ The rubrospinal tract is found to terminate in Rexed's laminae V-VII, with most ending in VI.^{88,91} Lamina VII contains a majority of neurons in the dorsal and lateral parts, with a small presence in the medial aspect.⁹² The medial component of lamina VII is largely responsible for axial and proximal muscle control.^{92,96} The ipsilateral pathway of the rubrospinal tract concludes in the intermediate zone in the cervical to upper thoracic spinal cord.⁹²

Termination

The feline RST terminates in Rexed's laminae VI,V (laterally), and laminae VII (medially and laterally).^{90,91} It is worth noting the somatotopic organization here, as well.⁹⁰ In cervical vertebrae, termination is observed at an identical location to that of rodents (Rexed's IX lamina).⁷⁶ With respect to the cervical vertebrae, RST fibers descend in the ventral aspect of the dorsolateral funiculus.⁹⁰ In the thoracic spine however, RST fibers descend dorsolaterally in the peripheral part of the lateral funiculus proximal to the dorsal horn within the lumbosacral enlargement.⁹⁰ The RST fibers enter the gray matter primarily in lamina VI (ventrally), but a presence in laminae V,VI, and VII has also been observed (laterally).⁹⁰

In the cervical spinal cord, the RST is not present in lamina VI.⁹⁰ After entering the gray matter, fibers propagate ventromedially to lamina V (lateral half), laminae VI (in its entirety but mostly laterally) and lamina VII (centrally as well as laterally).⁹⁰ There is not any termination in lamina IX, Clarke cells or in the intermediolateral cell column.⁹⁰ The thoracic cord is expected to follow the same pattern, with the key exception of a lack of presence in lamina VI.⁹⁰

3.2.5 HUMAN

There currently limited information regarding the human rubrospinal tract and its properties. Similar to the CST, information regarding the human RST is largely based on extrapolation from smaller animals and non-human primates (NHP), with a limited scope of information coming from diffusion weighted imaging (DWI) and histological assessment in humans.^{69,70,97,98}

Origin

Current research states the rubrospinal tract begins in the red nucleus.^{69-71,97,98} Two different cell types have been identified within the red nucleus, which has added to the complexity of identifying and understanding the RST relative to other tract systems. The magnocellular part of the red nucleus is composed of larger cells, which are thought to be the origin of the RST, as these fibers project to the spinal cord.⁷⁰ Smaller cells within the parvocellular region of the red nucleus do not project to the spinal cord and are thought to be part of the tegmento-spinal system.⁷⁰

Decussation

The RST fibers cross at the ventral tegmental decussation, in a lateral, oblique path, posterior to the medial lemniscus, passing into the reticular formation before reaching the gray matter of the anterior inferior cerebellar peduncle.^{69-71,97,98} The rubrospinal tract then enters the lateral aspect of the lateral lemniscus and continues descending to the descending trigeminal nucleus, and to the side of cranial nerve 7, as well as dorsomedial with respect to the superior olive.^{69-71,97,98}

Termination

There are currently conflicting theories for the termination of the rubrospinal tract within humans, with some showing that it does not extend beyond the C1-3 vertebrae, and others demonstrating that it reaches the beginning of the thoracic vertebrae.^{69,70}

3.3 VESTIBULOSPINAL TRACT

The vestibulospinal tract (VST) is another descending motor pathway that is important for maintaining posture and balance. In cats and humans, the VST has been characterized as having two components: the lateral vestibulospinal tract and the medial vestibulospinal tract.^{91,99} In humans, the lateral VST is associated with posture adjustments and limb reflex, while the medial VST has a role in the control of cranial orientation.¹⁰⁰ Early electrophysiology has also established the potential for connection between the VST and CST.¹⁰¹ In cats, the medial VST has been determined to effect function in the vestibulocollic reflex, localized to excitation and inhibition of neck muscles.^{102,103} The lateral VST acts in a highly specific manner, influencing a myriad of neuron types along the spinal cord.¹⁰⁴ To that extent it is understood that these neurons respond to input from other vestibular circuits and are subsequently responsible for postural adjustments of the head and neck.¹⁰⁴⁻¹⁰⁹ The VST is better defined in rodents and has also been shown to control posture and head movement, as well as vestibular startle response.^{110,111} While the VST is known to terminate in the upper thoracic spinal cord of humans, the VST has been shown to project to the lumbosacral spinal cord in rodents.^{112,113} These differences in projection locations is contributed to differing requirements for postural control, as humans are bipedal while rodents and cats are quadrupedal. This further highlights the importance of considering overall physiology when studying descending motor tracts for translation to humans.

3.3.1 SWINE

An intensive search including key terms such as “Vestibulospinal tract swine”, “pig vestibulospinal tract”, and “Swine vestibulospinal tract” was performed using the following databases: PubMed, Academic Search Ultimate, and Access Medicine, no results were found. Therefore, it is reasonable to draw the conclusion that direct knowledge of the pig VST is limited or unknown.

3.3.2 RAT

Search terms of the following: rat AND “lateral vestibulospinal”; rat AND “medial vestibulospinal” (no results); ((rat) AND (“vestibulospinal”)) AND (spinal cord) AND (“lateral”); “lateral/medial vestibulospinal” (no results), rat had limited information regarding the presence of a medial and/or lateral rat VST. Therefore, the rat VST will be discussed using the limited resources we have available.

Origin

Shamboul et al. used retrograde tracing to conclude that, similar to the VST of other species, rats also exhibit similar somatotopic organization of their VST.¹¹³ To that extent, it is believed that the caudal two thirds of the lateral vestibular nucleus (L_{Ve}) gives rise to tract fibers that terminate in the lumbar and sacral vertebrae and favor its dorsolateral aspect. The cranial two thirds of the L_{Ve} is responsible for projecting to thoracic and cervical segments, with cervical fibers propagating from the most cranial part of the L_{Ve}.¹¹³

Termination

Broadly speaking, the rodent vestibulospinal tract may be described as descending ipsilaterally, without decussation, and concluding largely in lamina VIII, medially in lamina VII and is present in motor neurons.¹¹⁴ VST fibers are also found in much higher amounts terminating at the spinal cord in areas associated with limb movement compared to those associated with the trunk.¹¹³ Even within the limbs division of VST fibers is found. The forelimbs receive three times the amount of VST fibers than the hindlimbs.¹¹³ This undoubtedly has an impact on the role of both the medial and lateral VST in rats and its contribution to locomotion.

3.3.3 MOUSE

The lateral VST in mice has been characterized to a far greater extent than the medial VST, but both exist with subjective boundaries.¹¹⁵⁻¹¹⁷ Current mouse research of the VST largely considers genetics and development.^{110,118,119}

Origin – Lateral VST

Liang, et al. completed a comprehensive map of the lateral VST using both anterograde and retrograde tracers and they have arrived at a similar conclusion: neurons of the lateral VST originate in the lateral vestibular nucleus (LVe). The projections then descend through, or lateral to the medial longitudinal fasciculus before travelling through their respective ipsilateral funiculi (ventral or lateral).¹¹⁵

Origin – Medial VST

As described above, the high degree of subjectivity in the border between the lateral and medial vestibular nuclei propagates difficulty where tractography is concerned.¹¹⁵ Thus, tractography work has established a unique, sparse populated of cells in the medial vestibular nucleus (MVe) that are considered the origin of the medial VST.¹¹⁵

Termination – Lateral VST

Termination of the lateral VST occurs ipsilaterally in the ventromedial gray matter of the spinal cord.¹¹⁵ Fibers were found terminating at all levels, cervical through sacral.¹¹⁵ Terminals were largely found ipsilaterally in Rexed's laminae VI, but are present in laminae VI – X, as well.¹¹⁵

Termination – Medial VST

Once more, the definition of the MVe and LVe has a significant impact on the termination of the tract. One definition states the medial VST terminates in the thoracic spinal cord.¹²⁰ While proposing a different organization of the borders of vestibular nuclei, Liang, et al. has used this definition to corroborate the termination of the medial VST in the ventral horns of cervical spinal cord segments.¹¹⁵

3.3.4 CAT

In a similar manner to other investigations, early investigation of the feline VST was performed using silver staining.¹²¹ Two anatomically distinct vestibulospinal tracts are present in cats, as well: the lateral VST and the medial VST.⁹¹ Research into the anatomy and physiology of the cat VST has decreased over time.¹²²⁻¹²⁴

Origin – Lateral VST

The lateral vestibulospinal tract begins at the LVe and descends the spinal cord homolaterally down the spinal cord's ventral funiculus.^{90,91,121} In the cervical spine, the lateral VST descends through the ventrolateral funiculus.⁹¹ As the tract descends through the thoracic cord it does so in a dorsomedial manner, before entering the lumbosacral enlargement (where they are present lateral to the anterior median fissure and medial to the ventral funiculus).⁹¹

Origin – Medial VST

The origin of the medial vestibulospinal tract can be localized to the medial vestibular nucleus (MVe). The medial VST is primarily located in the ventral funiculus, with 75% being found in the dorsal region.⁹¹

Termination – Lateral VST

Following the lumbosacral enlargement, the lateral VST terminates in laminae VII (medially and centrally) and VIII.⁹¹ When considering the thoracic region of the cord, specifically in the components of lamina VIII that cover the ventral horn, it is important to mention that termination occurs mostly in the medial aspect but is observed laterally as well.⁹¹ The majority of VST neurons terminate in the proximal cell processes, with a minority terminating in the somata.⁹¹

Termination – Medial VST

The medial VST progresses through the midthoracic vertebrae before terminating bilaterally in lamina VIII, and medially in lamina VII (in the higher half of the cord).⁹¹ With respect to the midthoracic region, more neurons exist on the homolateral side than the contralateral, which aligns with historical observations.^{91,125-127}

3.3.5 HUMAN

The human vestibulospinal tract is also separated into two components, the medial and lateral VST.⁹⁹ To the extent of the other human tracts, information largely relies on diffusion tensor tractography (DTT) imaging and experiments conducted in other vertebrates.^{99,100,128-132}

Lateral VST - Origin

DTT has also been used to characterize the lateral vestibulospinal cord and has identified its origin in the lateral vestibular nucleus. The lateral VST then descends through the posterolateral medulla (associated with the reticular formation) before ending anteriorly at the cervical lateral funiculus.⁹⁹ This proposed tract parallels the medial VST in the regard that both align with previous animal anatomic research.¹²⁹⁻¹³³

Origin - Medial VST

Diffusion tensor tractography (DTT) has been used to identify the human VST origin as the medial vestibular nuclei (with respect to the reticular formation). Following its origin, the tract then descends through the posterolateral medulla.^{99,100,128} This tract then descends bilaterally through the medial longitudinal fasciculus and continues through the anterior funiculus.¹³⁴

Lateral VST – Termination

The lateral VST tract terminates primarily on laminae VII and VIII, apart from a small amount of motor neuron endpoints.¹⁰⁰ To that extent, there exists both excitatory and inhibitory nerve cells here. The former functions through back, neck, and limb muscles, in addition to gamma neurons (theorized). The latter working through Ia inhibitory interneurons.⁶⁶

Termination – Medial VST

The medial VST concludes at the anterior cervical spinal cord (specifically the anterior component of the lateral funiculus) at laminae VII and VIII.^{99,100,128} This mechanism is consistent with previous research in animal models.^{99,129-133,135}

4. REGENERATIVE STRATEGIES FOR SPINAL CORD INJURY

One major sector of spinal cord injury (SCI) research is focused on axon regeneration, which has baffled researchers for decades. The reason being, axons within the central nervous system do not readily regenerate like axons within the peripheral nervous system. In fact, some therapies have included the use of peripheral nerve grafts/bridges to promote axonal reconnection following SCI, and have shown some promise, but the CNS microenvironment, particularly after injury, is not conducive to growth.^{136,137} Some species, like zebrafish and axolotls, have shown promise in the SCI field for their regenerative properties.^{138,139} Even a select species of mouse, the spiny mouse, has shown to have axon regeneration and improved functional recovery following complete spinal cord transection.¹⁴⁰ The clinical translation from these species to humans, however, is limited. Mammalian species like cats, primates, and rats have shown little-to-no spinal cord regeneration following injury, especially in the absence of pro-regenerative therapeutics. Of the research available that has shown spinal cord regeneration, it is difficult to say whether these observations are truly regenerative, a consequence of spared neural reorganization, or just experimental artifact.^{20,141-145} Even still, the lack of spinal cord regeneration among these species highlights the clinical relevance of their use in SCI research, but researchers should keep in mind the anatomical differences in descending motor tracts between the species, as mentioned above. To develop effective, regenerative therapeutics to treat SCI, researchers must consider the anatomy and physiology of humans and the animal models being used to recapitulate these injuries.

4.1 CURRENT RESEARCH FAVORS THE LARGE ANIMAL MODEL

As there are no FDA-approved therapeutics, biotechnology, or surgical interventions available to promote spinal cord regeneration, there is a critical need for an animal model with increased clinical relevance and translational fidelity, beyond the rat. Large animals, such as pigs and primates, are favored for SCI investigation due to the length and vasculature of their spinal cord being more comparable to that of a human.^{146,147} Pigs and primates are also comparable to humans with respect to overall larger anatomical size, metabolism, and immune responses, which are beneficial for optimizing devices, biomaterials and pharmacological treatments.^{4,146} Large animal models are also favored due to their complex cognitive and social behaviors.^{4,148,149} In fact, a survey consisting of academic and clinical practitioners appeared to favor the involvement of large animals in SCI research to increase translation of both non-invasive medications and invasive cell transplant therapies.¹⁵⁰ Further, an appropriate animal model is necessary by virtue of the sensitivity of motor tracts.⁷ Inappropriately altering motor tracts may result in harmful gain of function mechanisms like increased pain, spasticity, or autonomic dysreflexia.⁷ These key characteristics further highlight the necessity of an alternative model for CST regeneration, preferably a large animal.⁷

The two relevant large animal models for spinal cord regeneration are the non-human primate (NHP) and the pig. As described above, the relevance of both of these animals stems primarily from the incongruence between rat and

human spinal cord anatomy, with large animals having a similar organization of descending motor tracts. At the forefront of this argument are studies on rats, which following artificial unilateral severance of the CST, demonstrated that these tracts are not critical for locomotion.¹⁵¹ In contrast, damage to the CST in both humans and NHPs has devastating effects on locomotion, where walking significantly is impaired.¹⁵²⁻¹⁵⁵ Therefore, the usefulness of the NHP in spinal cord injury research is best summarized as the coalescence of the anatomical and functional similarities of fine motor control between primates and humans.¹⁵² The use of NHP for injury models also provides the opportunity to gain additional insight into and develop therapies with the goal of improving walking function.¹⁵²

Further foundational biological and logistical differences in anatomy and physiology have led to the investigation of swine for use in traumatic spinal cord injury.¹⁵⁶ NHPs certainly offer advantages in terms of spinal cord research but are not without their downfalls.^{152,156} Specifically, in addition to being more similar in anatomical size, pigs are more cost effective, offer potential for xenotransplantation, and are compatible for genome editing studies.^{156,157} This is further propagated by the logistical benefit of obtaining and training pigs, both of which are simpler than that of other animals.¹⁵⁶

4.2 THE CLINICAL STATUS OF ARTIFICIAL SPINAL CORD REGENERATION STRATEGIES

4.1.1 NOGO THERAPY

Despite evidence to the contrary, current research functions under the principal idea that spinal cord regeneration does not occur in natural settings and seeks to understand both why this happens, and how to artificially manipulate biological mechanism to regenerate long descending motor tracts (CST and RST).¹⁵⁸ Nogo-A has been identified as an inhibitor and is produced exclusively by neurons and oligodendroglia, which when bound to Nogo receptor 1, NgR1 (as opposed to NgR2 and NgR3), prevents axon regeneration.¹⁵⁸⁻¹⁶² When Nogo-66 was used to disallow Nogo receptor function, CST regeneration and amelioration was observed.^{158,163,164} In rats and monkeys, when Nogo-A was affected with antibodies, an improvement in spinal cord recovery was observed.^{158,165,166} Nogo A has also been observed to interact in conjunction with myelin-associated glycoprotein (MAG) and oligodendroglial myelin glycoprotein (OMgp) to decrease CST recovery in mice.¹⁶⁷

Many laboratories have confirmed the ability of additional ligands, specifically MAG and oligodendroglia myelin glycoprotein (OMgp), to interact with the Nogo-66 receptor and restrict fiber regeneration via growth cone inhibition.¹⁶⁸⁻¹⁷¹ While earlier works have described a lack of OMgp, MAG, Nogo and Nogo-66 binding to NgR2 and 3, contemporary literature has shown MAG-NgR2 binding activity.^{159,172}

4.1.2 COMPLICATIONS OF NOGO THERAPY

Two compounding factors complicate the NOGO therapy, its function as the foremost inhibitor of long descending tract regeneration has been challenged by genetic and other studies.¹⁵⁸ While research found CST regeneration in mice after SCI as a result of Nogo silencing, other studies contradict the finding that Nogo silencing leads to CST regeneration.¹⁷³⁻¹⁷⁶ Adding to the complexity of the Nogo receptor and its implications, the NgR1 receptor appears to demonstrate involvement in both development (through the existence of OMgp, MAG and Nogo ligands and receptors in maturation) and recovery of mental function after injury.^{171,177,178}

4.1.3 RHO-A/ROCK (RHO-KINASE) THERAPY

Ultimately, the ligands discussed above (specifically Nogo, MAG and OMgp) function to activate Rho A and its effector Rho-Kinase (ROCK).^{158,179} These receptors bind GTP.¹⁵⁸ Similar to other molecules involved in cell signal transduction, ROCK plays an integral role in many different pathways and regulation, but the most significant for this review is its role in cellular motility (via cytoskeleton), neurite growth cones, and the prevention of nerve fiber regrowth.^{158,180-192} Rho-A/ROCK activity is affected in the spinal cord chiefly by injury and synthesized substances, leading it to be the subject of spinal cord regeneration research.¹⁵⁸

Injury has been shown to activate Rho activity and inhibit regrowth, and experimental inactivation has been shown to propagate spinal cord regeneration in rat subjects.^{193,194} A separate developmental procedure describes the incorporation of BA-210 (a Rho-inactivator) into the dura mater of both rats and mice following SCI has improved locomotion.¹⁹⁵ The use of this medication has also shown similar benefit in clinical trials and is the subject of continuing research to fully understand its effectiveness and role (if any) in the treatment of SCI.¹⁹⁶

4.1.4 COMPLICATIONS OF RHO-A/ROCK THERAPY

Over the counter (OTC) medications have also been demonstrated to affect Rho-A/ROCK, however this is met with significant skepticism.¹⁵⁸ While some groups have reported the successful use of NSAID's for remyelination, Rho inhibition, as well as protection against secondary injury and regeneration, this has yet to be replicated amongst other researchers.¹⁹⁷⁻¹⁹⁹ The other major medication of interest is Fasudil, which inhibits ROCK and is currently already

in clinical use (although not for spinal cord regeneration).¹⁵⁸ However, it is met with similar skepticism and a consensus remains to be drawn on its role in SCI therapy.²⁰⁰

4.1.5 GLIAL SCAR THERAPY

Another experimental approach to improving the outcomes of SCI regeneration is the manipulation of glial scars, though surgical or medicinal techniques.^{201,202} Research also indicates that glial scars do not positively or negatively impact the initiation of axon growth, however the glial scar is inhibitory of axon growth once fibrosis is completed.^{158,202} Surgical interventions, by means of dissecting the glial scar and transplanting neural stem cells, mesenchymal stem cells or umbilical cord blood cells have also been developed with the aim of promoting regeneration.^{158,201,203-207}

4.1.6 ISSUES WITH GLIAL SCAR THERAPIES

Treatments altering or decreasing glial scar formation have shown an improvement of motor function in rodents, in addition to detrimental effects such as decreased motor function, deleterious effects on blood brain barrier repair, and further cellular damage.²⁰⁸⁻²¹² Furthermore, altering rate and expression of the cell cycle has been shown to contribute to further disrupt regular spinal cord function.^{158,213}

4.1.7 CHONDROITIN SULFATE PROTEOGLYCAN THERAPY

Chondroitin sulfate is a sulfated glycosaminoglycan (GAG) comprised of glucuronic acid and *N*-acetylgalactosamine, which exist in the extracellular matrix between astrocytes and peripheral tissues.^{158,214} The proteins affixed to chondroitin sulfate are termed chondroitin sulfate proteoglycans (CSPG).¹⁵⁸ Chondroitinase ABC, or ChABC is an enzyme responsible for disconnecting GAG from proteoglycans and has been approached by many different teams as a potential therapy in the promotion of spinal cord recovery.^{158,215} Early research has shown that CSPG concentration increased alongside and at sites of surgically induced injury, as well as establishing the notion that ChABC cleaves CSPG.²¹⁶

4.1.8 ChABC INJECTION APPROACH

Treatment of spinal cord injury with ChABC has shown regeneration of Clarke's neurons, which compose the dorsal spinocerebellar tract.²¹⁷ Also in rats, ChABC spinal injection has demonstrated the restoration of sensation after nerve root rhizotomy.²¹⁸ ChABC may also exhibit influence over peripheral nerve repair, as spinal cord ChABC injections increased functionality; although a mechanism for this phenomenon is not currently established.²¹⁹ In conjunction with physical therapy (PT), ChABC improved dexterity (a function associated with the CST in rats) after an induced cervical dorsal funiculus injury.^{220,221} In cats, similar improvements have been characterized following ChABC injections, however tract tracing implicates the RST as the explanation for improved recovery.⁹⁴ The intraventricular injection of ChABC into the rat has demonstrated a statistical recovery improvement after damage to the dorsal columns and CST.²²² After subdural placement of a gel plate containing ChABC over a CST injury, the amount of GAG was decreased 37% relative to injections, and exhibited a 5 fold lesser concentration when compared to a control group that did not receive treatment.²²³ The results mentioned above, especially concerning rat models, have been explored extensively and other authors have largely reported similar results.^{217,224-227}

4.1.9 ChABC INTRATHECAL PUMPS/CATHETERS

Current research involving intrathecal methods of introducing ChABC into the spinal cord has demonstrated an increase in rat CST regeneration.²²⁸ In mice the intrathecal introduction of ChABC has further established the function of CSPG's as axon regrowth limiting agents.²²⁹ Further rat research regarding the use of intrathecal pumps after SCI shows that the motor effects and improvements from ChABC incorporation are likely a function of decreasing GAG concentration, as opposed to CSPG protein reduction.²³⁰ The improvement of regenerative properties via intrathecal pump are verified across many laboratories, although the extent of its effectiveness remains a subject of future interest.^{231,232}

4.1.10 ADDITIONAL DELIVERY METHODS

The use of a virus intermediate to continuously introduce ChABC is also being explored, which eliminates the need for multiple procedures, and has been shown to promote neuronal regrowth.²²⁹

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Considering the neuroanatomy of the species mentioned and the clinical status of regenerative spinal cord therapies, it is clear that there are costs and benefits to both small and large animal models of SCI which each offer a unique framework to study specific mechanisms and outcomes of injury. Rodent models do not have as much anatomical relevance to study specific descending motor tracts in detail but are still useful for the development of molecular

mechanistic-based therapeutics. Pigs are more similar to humans in anatomical size, physiology, spinal cord composition and organization, and immune response, which makes them ideal models to study the motor and molecular consequences of SCI. As outlined in this review, the descending motor tracts of the pig should be further characterized for their use in SCI research as contemporary neuroanatomical work highlights potential clinical and economic benefits of pig research. Compared to non-human primates, pigs are more cost effective and offer just as much, if not more insight into the specific neuroanatomical and physiological impact of SCI. Research in pigs can bridge the translational research gap between what we have learned in rodents to what we observe in humans so that effective mechanistic-based therapies, biomaterials, and devices can be created to treat SCI. Current work suggests that spinal cord regeneration (and a lack thereof) is a coalescence of many receptor-ligand interactions and physiologic regulation; all of which complicate artificial manipulation of long descending motor tracts. A more complete understanding of the variances between animal models of SCI will lead to more effective therapies that translate to human SCI patients.

SUMMARY TABLES

CST	Origin	Decussation	Termination
Pig	Motor cortex	84.9% decussate at pyramids 15.1% decussate at pyramids*	At least T6, possibly lower
Rat	Motor cortex	90% decussate at pyramids 10% of fibers continue ipsilaterally	Rexed's laminae
Mouse	Motor cortex	Pyramids	Rexed's laminae
Cat	Motor cortex	75%-95% decussate at pyramids 25%-5% of fibers continue ipsilaterally*	Rexed's laminae, lumbar levels
Human	Motor cortex	75-90% decussation at pyramids 25%-10% decussate continue ipsilaterally*	Rexed's laminae

Table 1: Summary of the corticospinal (CST) tract. The origin, decussation point, and termination across pigs, rats, mice, cats, and humans is briefly described. *: Percentage of ipsilateral fibers were extrapolated using the established ratio of decussating fibers.

RST	Origin	Decussation	Termination
Pig	No information available	No information available	No information available
Rat	Red nucleus	Tegmentum	Rexed's laminae IX All vertebrae levels
Mouse	Red nucleus	Tegmentum	Rexed's laminae
Cat	Red nucleus	Tegmentum	Rexed's laminae
Human	Red nucleus	Tegmentum	Research uncertain, both C1-3 and upper thoracic terminations proposed

Table 2: Summary of the rubrospinal (RST) tract. The origin, decussation point, and termination across pigs, rats, mice, cats, and humans is briefly described.

VST	Origin	Decussation	Termination
Pig	No information available	Does not decussate	No information available
Rat	Vestibular nucleus	Does not decussate	Rexed's VIII, some in VII
Mouse	Vestibular nucleus	Does not decussate	Lateral: Rexed's laminae
Cat		Does not decussate	
Human	Vestibular nucleus	Does not decussate	Rexed's laminae

Table 3: Summary of the vestibulospinal tract, an extrapyramidal tract that does not decussate. The origin and termination across pigs, rats, mice, cats, and humans is briefly described.

	Swine	Rodent	Cat	Man
CST	Similar neuronal distribution to man across dorsolateral, ventromedial and dorsomedial funiculus.	CST present in dorsal spinal cord. Similar scarring patterns to man.	CST exhibits dorsal and ventral components.	CST in lateral spinal cord. Primary tract for locomotion. Dorsal and ventral aspects present.
RST	Axial and proximal muscle control.	Primary tract for locomotion	Not well characterized. Low evidence to support presence in lamina IV.	Secondary (proposed) locomotive tract.
VST	No information available/not characterized.	Stimulatory/sensory only.	Medial/lateral VST present. Functions in posture, limb reflex.	Medial and lateral VST present. Functions in posture, limb reflex.

Table 4: Physiologic summary of vertebrate long descending motor tracts

	NOGO Therapy	RHO-Kinase (ROCK) Therapy	Glial Scar Therapy	Chondroitin Sulfate Proteoglycan (ChABC) Therapy
Complications	Contradictory evidence concerning role of NOGO in inhibition of spinal cord regeneration. NgR1 receptor involved in multiple pathways, complicating treatment options.	Results showing regeneration have not been replicated. Similar complications to those of NOGO. Mechanism not fully understood.	Altering cell cycle may result in deleterious conditions (decreased motor function, cellular damage, damage to blood-brain barrier). May disrupt other spinal cord functions.	RST regeneration may be the result of locomotive regeneration. Efficacy of treatment requires further evaluation.

Table 5: Summary of current SCI treatments and their complications.

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